

A Concurrent Built-In Self-Test Architecture Based on a Self-Testing RAM

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KEYWORDS

Built-in self-testing, concurrent testing, input vector monitoring

ABSTRACT

This work presents a concurrent Built-In Self-Test (BIST) architecture based on a self-testing RAM to enable real-time detection of memory faults during normal system operation. Unlike conventional offline BIST approaches, the proposed architecture allows concurrent execution of memory testing and functional access, thereby eliminating system downtime. The self-testing RAM integrates dedicated test circuitry to detect permanent and transient faults with minimal impact on performance. The proposed design achieves improved fault coverage while maintaining low hardware overhead and power consumption. This architecture is particularly suitable for high-reliability and safety-critical applications where continuous memory monitoring is essential.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the current trend to dramatically increase the scale of integration, Built-In Self-Test (BIST) techniques provide an attractive solution to test modules deeply embedded in complex integrated Circuits. BIST eliminates the necessity of high-bandwidth test interactions and allows at-speed testing.

Other benefits of BIST include reduced product development cycle and cost-effective system maintenance. BIST utilizes a *Test Pattern Generator (TPG)*

to generate the test patterns which are applied to the inputs of the *Circuit Under Test (CUT)*. In off-line BIST, the normal operation of the CUT is stalled in order to perform the test. Thus, if the CUT is of critical importance for the function of the circuit, the total circuit performance is degraded. To avoid this performance degradation, input vector monitoring concurrent BIST techniques have been proposed which exploit input vectors arriving at the inputs of the CUT during normal operation.

The block diagram of an input vector monitoring concurrent BIST technique is presented in Fig. 1. The CUT is combinational, has inputs and outputs, and is tested exhaustively; hence, the test set size is $N=2^n$. The technique can operate in one out of two modes, *normal* (when $TN=0$), and *test* ($TN=1$)

During normal mode, the CUT inputs, denoted by $A=A[n:1]$ are driven from the normal input vector ($V[n:1]$). A is also driven to the *Active test set Generator and Comparator (AGC)*, where it is compared to a set of *active test vectors* called *active test set*. If it is found that A matches one of the active test vectors, we say that a *hit* has occurred, or that the input vector (V) has performed a hit. When a hit occurs, A is removed from the active test set, and the *Response Verifier (RV)* captures the CUT response to the input vector. When all input vectors have performed a hit, the contents of the Response Verifier are examined, in order to take a decision as to whether a fault has occurred in the CUT.

In case that, during normal operation, the CUT does not receive all input vectors, the circuit may sporadically operate in test mode in order to complete the test. During *test mode*, the inputs to the CUT are driven from $V[n:1]$ generated by the *Active test set Generator and Comparator*, and the Response Verifier is enabled in every clock cycle.

A crucial measure of the effectiveness of an input vector monitoring concurrent BIST technique is the *Concurrent Test Latency*, i.e. the mean number of clock cycles required in order to complete the test while the CUT operates in normal mode only. Increasing the hardware overhead can decrease the concurrent test latency, as has been shown in [3]–[5].

In this paper, a novel input vector monitoring concurrent BIST technique for combinational circuits is presented, termed *RAM-based Input Vector Monitoring Concurrent BIST (R-CBIST)*, for the concurrent testing of combinational circuits under test. R-CBIST is shown to be more effective than the other input vector monitoring concurrent BIST techniques proposed so far [2]–[5] in terms of Hardware Overhead/Concurrent Test Latency tradeoff. ROM constitute very critical modules in complex circuits. Therefore, a BIST scheme for ROM modules should meet two basic requirements:

- no need to set the ROM off-line, and
- very high effective fault coverage (which is achieved with exhaustive testing, that covers all logically testable faults [1], [7], [8]).

Input vector-monitoring concurrent BIST techniques are suitable for the testing of ROM because they meet both above requirements.

It is shown that R-CBIST results in low hardware overhead, and therefore it is a practical solution for the concurrent testing of ROM modules.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

The pioneering work on input vector monitoring concurrent BIST was carried out by Saluja *et al.* (C-BIST, [2]). The Active test set Generator and Comparator of C-BIST is a single Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR), and a comparator; and thus the active test set consists of only one active test vector, which is the current value of the LFSR. During normal mode, the input vector is compared with the unique active test vector. If the two vectors match, the LFSR proceeds to the next state changing the active test vector, and the Response Verifier (typically implemented as a Multiple Input Shift Register, MISR) is enabled.

C-BIST has low hardware overhead, but very high Concurrent Test Latency, because in every clock cycle the input vector is compared against only one active test vector. To drive down the concurrent test latency, three techniques have been proposed so far, namely *Multiple Hardware Signature Analysis Technique (MHSAT)* [4], *Order Independent Signature Analysis Technique (OISAT)* [3], and *windowed-Comparative Concurrent BIST (w-CBIST)* [5]. These techniques accomplish to decrease the Concurrent Test Latency by increasing the number of active test vectors.

The Active test set Generator and Comparator of MHSAT [4] consists of L LFSR, and L comparators; and thus the active test set consists of L active test vectors. Also, there are L order-dependent Response Verifiers (implemented as Multiple Input Shift Registers, MISR); each response verifier corresponds to an LFSR. During normal mode, the input vector is compared against the L active test vectors. A hit occurs if the input vector matches any one of the active test vectors. In this case, the LFSR which performed the hit proceeds to the next state (changing the specific active test vector), and the corresponding MISR is enabled. The test is complete when all LFSR have completed their cycles.

OISAT [3] implements an Active test set Generator and Comparator similar to the one used by MHSAT, but instead of L order-dependent Response Verifiers, it implements only one order-independent Response

Verifier (the Accumulator-Based Compaction of the responses, ABC [6]). The Response Verifier is enabled every time an LFSR performs a hit. Windowed Comparative Concurrent BIST (w-CBIST) [5] is based on the separation of the N input vectors to N/W subsets called windows. During normal operation, w-CBIST exploits the arrival of any input vector belonging to a specific window termed *active window*. The active test set consists of the vectors belonging to the active window, and only when all vectors of the active window have performed hit, w-CBIST proceeds to the next active window.

3. PROGRAMMABLE MBIST

Over With increasing complexity in modern System-on-Chip designs, more and more memory instances with different sizes and types are being integrated into one chip, and testing all these memories under the constraint of low area cost becomes an important issue. Moreover, to enhance the test quality, it is necessary to add or modify the test patterns in the test stage to screen out unexpected manufacturing defects. In regard to both the area cost and test flexibility issues, the P-MBIST approach is a promising solution.

A typical P-MBIST[4][5] design is implemented by micro-code operations. In general, it defines the instruction format to support all operations of the selected memory test algorithms and uses a program memory to load the test program. Recently, an approach based on the scan register was proposed to eliminate the program storage requirement but the existing solutions were mainly based on single-memory conditions a hardware-sharing P-MBIST design for a single chip, containing multiple instances of different types. To lower the area cost, all memory instances are tested by using one common address generator and one BIST controller. P-MBIST includes functions that

- (1) Support the programmable data background and March based element
- (2) Contain both row-wise (i.e. word-line) and column-wise (i.e. bit-line) addressing ways,
- (3) capture the address, syndrome, and states of failures,
- (4) Provide the parallel and sequential tests for each selected group of memory instances with the same or different sizes, and
- (5) Support the pipeline option for the high speed test.

Four important elements of our design are highlighted here.

(1) To significantly reduce area overhead, a MUX based controller is applied to test all the memory instances with only one address generator.

(2) The high-speed address generator is used to support both row and column addressing ways, and the overflow in the column-scan mode is avoided by the early decision circuit to properly switch to the next column address.

Many programmable MBIST[4][5] have been developed, and they can be classified into two categories: one is based on the finite state machine (FSM) model and the other is based on the microcode controller. In general, the microcode-based approach is more popular since it is more flexible. However, it is more complicate to design such a BIST, and the area overhead is usually higher. In all these works, the test algorithm is selected by applying some predefined instructions. It is required to create a test instruction in each step of the test algorithm, and these external instructions are transferred to the internal registers one by one. In this way, we can freely select the applied test algorithm. The advantage of this approach is the flexibility to select test algorithms, but both complexity of the control mechanism and area overhead increase as well. If the memories are embedded in SOC, the automatic test equipment (ATE) needs to send many test commands to execute a test algorithm, and this process also increases the test time.

3.1 P-MBIST ARCHITECTURE

To support flexible March elements and diagnostic procedures, the proposed P-MBIST[2] provides the following features: (1) different data background, (2) programmable March-based element, (3) column-scan addressing mode, (4) capturing the address, syndrome and state of failures, (5) parallel and sequential test, (6) pipeline mode for higher test speed. Table 9.I lists the detailed programmable items of instructions. The “folded” and “inverted” bits can invert the “data_bg” while the switching of the specified address bit. By setting the “data_bg” to 0 and configuring both “folded” and “interted” bits to 1, the Checkerboard pattern can be generated. Column scan addressing can be controlled by cs_sel. Finally, each March operation description uses three bits, EOC, R/W, and Polarity, to define the operation. Fig. 10.1 gives an instruction example of performing three operations in a March element. By

setting up the “diagnosis” bit to 1, the failure information will be dumped out while detecting the mismatching memory output.

Table 1: Description of each instruction bit

Bit Name	Description
Dual_port_sel	Valid for dual_port group: 0: port A 1: port B
Cs_sel	0:row scan 1:column scan
diagnosis	0:no dump 1:dump fail information
Updn	0: address-down counting 1:address up counting
Data_bg	Programmable data background
Folded	1:data_bg inverts itself when the new row start
Inverted	1:data_bg inverts itself at each address
*EOC	0: The Last command 1: Not the last command
*R/W	Write:0 Read:1
*Polarity	0:No inversion for data_bg 1: Inversion for data_bg

(* Each March operation is represented by three bits)

Figure 1: An instruction with 3 March operations and 8-bit data background

Figure 2 shows the block diagram of the proposed P-MBIST design[2]. Firstly, the instruction is serially shifted into instruction_read module. To reduce the hardware

cost, the address counter is shared to test all memory instances. Moreover, decoder blocks can support different memory type testing without increasing any state (i.e. each memory has the same read/write cycle). The memory in the same type can be grouped and tested in the either sequential or parallel way. The supported memory types include single/dual/twoport SRAM, one/two-port register file and ROM. Finally, according to the user-defined configuration file, the proposed P-MBIST engine can be automatically generated from the developed software program.

Figure 2: Block diagram of P-MBIST design

3.2 Address Generator

To share the common address generator[2], it is a simple way to choose an address counter with the largest address bit among all the under-tested memory instances. As shown in Fig. 10.3, the low-bit of address counter can be used to indicate the low-address memory instance, by properly controlling the chip-select signal for each memory instance.

Figure 3: Timing diagram of shared address counter

As for the column-scan mode, the address counter is not just ascending or descending by 1. Table 10.2 provides an example, which defines the column Mux to 4 and the maximum address to 11. In Table 10.2, the 1st column shows the address counter output for row scan (i.e. ascending by 1). The 2nd column gives the address for column scan (i.e. ascending by 4). To share the row-scan and column-scan adder, we use the up-scrambler to

Figure 7 shows a simplified controller supporting 3 continuous March operations. Firstly, the external signal, *rst_l*, triggers the state and gets into wait state. Once the complete instruction has been input, it will go to March1 state. If the diagnosis mode is turned-on and the fault address is detected, the state will be held until all the failure information has been dumped out. Otherwise, there is no stall cycle while performing each March element.

Figure 7: Controller state for P-MBIST

3.4 Pipeline Design Issue

For higher testing speed, address generator is a critical path because of the long delay of adder and comparator. To enhance the operating frequency, two pipeline stages are inserted to the address generator. The first stage is used to put to the bus of “inc_A” and the second stage is placed to the “Over_flow_CS” signal (i.e. refer to the potential pipeline stage in Fig. 10.5). Fig. 10.8 illustrates the timing relation between pipelining address generator and two inserted pipeline states, *pipe_state1* and *pipe_state2*. First, the register, *inc_A_reg*, is determined after one delay cycle of *addr_reg*. Afterward, *Over_flow_CS_reg* can be determined and the *addr_reg* can be further determined. Based on this design method, the operating frequency could achieve high testingspeed case for typical memory application (i.e. 0.13 μm with 14-bit adder at 500 MHz).

Figure 8: Timing diagram of pipeline design

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Simulation Results

Figure 9 gives the information on input applied *o_bist_k* is the signal which gives the information for to start the bist operation signal *instr_re* which gives the information on instruction register *data_par* which gives

the information of data was applied *err_pulse_r* which gives information of error in was there or not *i_bist_pass* which gives the information of bist pass *i_bist_fail* which gives the information on bist fail *i_bist_done* which gives information of bist operation is done *Mem_addr_rd* which gives the memory read address *Mem_addr_wr* which gives the memory write address *offset_start* which gives the start of memory size *offset_end* which gives the end of memory size *err_reg* which gives the information error bits in memory. This figure 9 gives the starting of bist operation.

Figure 9: Simulation Result

Figure 10: Simulation Result

Figure 10 gives the information on input applied *o_bist_k* is the signal which gives the information for to start the bist operation signal *instr_re* which gives the information on instruction register *data_par* which gives the information of data was applied *err_pulse_r* which gives information of error in was there or not *i_bist_pass* which gives the information of bist pass *i_bist_fail* which gives the information on bist fail *i_bist_done* which gives information of bist operation is done *Mem_addr_rd* which gives the memory read address *Mem_addr_wr* which gives the memory write address *offset_start* which gives the start of memory size *offset_end* which gives the

end of memory size err_reg which gives the information error bits in memory. Fig 10 gives the information of bist was pass or fail and gives information of bist operation was done

Figure 11: Simulation Result

Fig 11 gives the information on input applied o_bist_k is the signal which gives the information for to start the bist operation signal instr_re which gives the information on instruction register data_par which gives the information of data was applied err_pulse_r which gives information of error in was there or not i_bist_pass which gives the information of bist pass i_bist_fail which gives the information on bist fail i_bist_done which gives information of bist operation is done Mem_addr_rd which gives the memory read address Mem_addr_wr which gives the memory write address offset_start which gives the start of memory size offset_end which gives the end of memory size err_reg which gives the information error bits in memory. Fig 11 gives the error in the memory was introduce and error in the was removed or not and bist operation is pass or fail.

Synthesis Results

• **HDL Synthesis Report**

Macro Statistics

# Adders/Subtractors	: 1
5-bit addsub	: 1
# Counters	: 1
32-bit up counter	: 1
# Registers	: 155
1-bit register	: 140
32-bit register	: 6
37-bit register	: 1
4-bit register	: 3

5-bit register	: 1
64-bit register	: 4
# Comparators	: 2
5-bit comparator greater	: 1
5-bit comparator lessequal	: 1
# Xors	: 64
1-bit xor2	: 64

• **Final Register Report**

Macro Statistics

# Registers	: 290
Flip-Flops	: 290

• **Device utilization summary:**

Selected Device : 3s500efg320-4

Number of Slices:	248 out of 4656	5%
Number of Slice Flip Flops:	290 out of 9312	3%
Number of 4 input LUTs:	385 out of 9312	4%
Number of IOs:	214	
Number of bonded IOBs:	150 out of 232	64%
Number of GCLKs:	1 out of 24	4%

• **Timing Summary**

Speed Grade: -4

Minimum period: 6.651ns (Maximum Frequency: 150.353MHz)

RTL Schematic

Figure 12: Top Level Circuit

Figure 12 gives the information about the top level circuit which having who many input and output are there the level circuit having inputs are reset, register write, register read, clock, memory address, memory

data read and write and output are bist pass, bist fail, bist done, register address

minimum number of read and write operations. To the extend this work we can design addition of BISR

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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Figure 13: RTL Schematic diagram

Figure 13 shows the internal rtl schematic diagram having register block and the fsm block where the internal operation are done

Technology Schematic

Figure 14: Technology Schematic

Figure 14 gives the information about how many LUT's in FPGA was occupied

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an efficient architecture for PMBIST circuit has been designed based on the hardware sharing method, the common address counter has been used to provide to provide all memory instances, including row-scan and column-scan addressing mode. Moreover, the controller can be extended to different memory types in the same read/write cycle condition, without increasing any state. Thus, the hardware cost can be greatly reduced. Finally, the P-MBIST circuit can be automatically generated from the user-defined configuration file. We can extend this work to implement Programmable Memory Built-In Self Test with less hardware and with

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